

CAST 4th NEWSLETTER

June 2022

Active Monitoring of Cancer AS an Alternative To Surgery

MARIE SKLODOWSKA-CURIE GRANT PROJECT

Colophon

The CAST Newsletter is to inform all participants and those interested in the CAST. We will share publications, presentations and news. The CAST Newsletter is also sent to participants in the IWWD-consortium.

If you like to be added to the mailing list or if you want to be removed, please mail to CAST@lumc.nl

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Early Stage Researchers

This Newsletter was created by the 15 CAST ESRs together:

Ignacio, Bitu, Ngu, Ilaria, Somayeh, Sofieke, Rita, Lishan, Bharti, Felicia, Shabnam, Francesco, Ana and Elham.

Our first in-person meeting!

On May 18th and 19th 2022, all the members of the CAST consortium came together for the **first in-person meeting** since the beginning of the project. It has been an enormous pleasure to meet all the fellow researchers in person, after we have only seen each other through a screen for a very long time, for some of us over 2 years.

Finally, we could set a long step forward in some of the main CAST objectives: collaborating and networking goes much smoother when you talk to real people!

In these two days, each ESR presented their research, including their preliminary results and future plans in different work packages. Each presentation was followed by intensive discussion and feedback from the fellow researchers. This brain storming resulted in new collaborations, and, we look forward to seeing its outcome in our upcoming newsletters!

We learnt extensively about our fellow colleagues' research. The Karolinska Institute gave a wonderful platform to practice our presentation skills, finally in front of a real audience!

The CAST family keeps growing!

The month of May started with a wonderful surprise: Ignacio and his wife became parents to this beautiful little child.

Welcome in the CAST family, little Bruno.

The photo and the news have been published with the permission of the young parents

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 857894

Presentations to the CAST public

Some photos from the presentations from our ESRs: on the left Felicia (ESR13) and Francesco (ESR12) presenting on WP 2.3; in the middle Somayah (ESR2) who participates in WP 2.2, 2.5 and 2.8; on the right Bita (ESR 11 on WP2.5) and Ignacio (ESR5) who joined us digitally from home and presented on WP 2.6.

But not only presentations!

We had some lovely dinners in vibrant, ornate restaurants and got to know each other also aside our working time.

Somayah and Francesco (ESRs 2 and 12) have taken the concept of **dissemination to the public** very seriously. Here they are discussing CAST and our visit to Stockholm with a local in front of the Nobel Prize Museum

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Rectal Cancer Forum 2022

On Friday May 20th all CAST members were invited to the Rectal Cancer Forum, organized by Karolinska University in Stockholm. This event brought together some of the most influential international experts on the topic of rectal cancer, for the occasion also called Rectal Rock Stars.

All presentations were interesting and educational. Topics ranged from surgery to Watch & Wait, from radiologic diagnosis through MRI and molecular imaging to the best radiotherapeutic regimens: external beam as well as contact brachytherapy, from immunotherapy to the role liquid biopsy. All these subjects play a big role in the CAST and that is the reason why our ESRs are doing research in each of these very relevant fields for the management of rectal cancer.

During the event Somayeh, Rita, Bharti, Shabnam, Francesco and Elham presented their posters to the international audience.

Dinner at the National Museum

The Rectal Cancer Forum was not only about presenting and learning, but it also gave some of us the chance to have a really unique dinner inside the Stockholm National Museum.

Our hosts in Stockholm together with the CAST management team really did a great job to make all of this possible!

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Multicultural environment among ESRs

During these dinners ESRs got to know more about the cultural aspects of the countries they come from. Our ESRs come from Asia, Europe and Latin America.

The multicultural environment inspires creativity and promotes innovation. The ESRs got an opportunity to exchange the local scientific ethics and insights, and introspect on pros and cons of different work cultures. We believe this promotes cultural sensitivity, insight, tolerance, acceptance and incorporation in the ESRs at early stages in their careers.

*From left to right:
Elham from Iran
Ngu from Myanmar
Margarita from Greece
Bharti from India
Somayeh from Iran
Ana from Albania*

The ESRs also had the chance to be presented with a piece of Scandinavian culture at the dinner held in the National Museum of Sweden and the lovely choir that sang a few traditional songs. **Tack så mycket!**

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CAST ESRs page

Our self presentation page is ON!
On the official CAST website, since April 2022 you can find a section dedicated to us ESRs. Each of us introduced him or herself, so that you can know more of our backgrounds, our interests, our current projects, our publications. Plus, you can easily find us on LinkedIn and Twitter and quickly see our publications.

What are you waiting for? Click on this [link](#) and you will easily access the page and learn more about us!

Social Media

We are doing our best to share all our activities on social media.
Do not forget to follow us on:

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As a sad concluding note, we would like to thank Margarita Karageorgou for sharing this first part of CAST experience with us. Unfortunately, Margarita recently decided to resign from the CAST project and to continue her bright career as a surgeon on a different path. We wish her all the best for her life and her career!

This also means that a vacancy is open for a new ESR in Liverpool at the Clatterbridge Cancer Center, starting as soon as possible. If you are interested in the position or know someone who would be interested in applying, you can find more information at this [link](#) or send all your information to this mail address: jobs@cast-cancer.eu.

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